

**New subspecies of *Cerambyx cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Central Russia**

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Abstract: *Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo nikolaevi* **ssp. n.** is described from Samara environs. The new subspecies is widely distributed in steppe zone of Eastern Europe.

Introduction

Cerambyx cerdo Linnaeus, 1758 was described as “Habitat in Italia. M. Kähler. in Germania.” The species is widely distributed along northern Palaearctic Region from Iberic Peninsula to European Russia, North Africa, Near East and Caucasus (Danilevsky, 2020). The species is characterized by great geographical and individual variability. Many subspecies were described and traditionally accepted (up to 8), though the number of infraspecific taxa varied from author to author. Certain authors (Sama, 2003) finally were not able to accept any subspecies, because the most peculiar one - *C. c. mirbecki* Lucas, 1842 from North Africa includes specimens indistinguishable from *C. c. cerdo* from Western Europe. But statistically many geographical forms can be easily recognized. New subspecies continue to be described up to now as new populations are studied. So, recently *C. c. masaryki* Vartanis, 2018 from Bulgaria and *C. c. cyprius* Vartanis, 2023 from Cyprus were described.

Meanwhile no specimens of *C. cerdo* were known from central part of European Russia to Plavilstshikov (1940, 1965 - West of Ukraine, Crimea, Caucasus), neither to (Aurivillius, 1912). But K.V. Arnoldi (1953: 179) widened its area eastwards to about Volga (K.V. Arnoldi, 1953: 179). The species was known to him

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(K.V. Arnoldi, 1953: 185) from Tellerman Forest in Voronezh Region and was also recorded for Voronezh Region by Polozhentsev, Alekseev (1959), Negrobov et al. (2005).

C. cerdo was recorded for Ulyanovsk Region by Isaev et al. (2004), Isaev (2004 - Bakhteevka), for Samara Region by Dyuzhaeva & Lyubvina (2000), for Orenburg Region by Simonenkova & Yakimov (2007), for Penza region by Polumordvinov & Monakhov (2007, 2019), for Chuvashia (Cheboksary) by Fadeev, Moskovkin (1979) and Sysoletina, Khmel'kov (1984 - near Cheboksary). Two males from Samara Region (one dated 1956, another one from Zhiguli: 12.7.1973 D.Naturo leg.) are preserved in Samara Natural Museum (D. Magdeev, personal message 2018). One male from Samara ("Kuybyshev, Frunze, 24.5.1975") is preserved in author's collection.

It was included in Red Data Book of many Russian regions: Tatarstan (Khalidov, 1995), Lipetsk (Tsurikov, 2006), Kursk (Dyachenko, 2017), Voronezh (Negrobov & Maslova, 2018), Belgorod (Prisnyi, 2019).

The adequate construction of infraspecific taxonomy of *C. cerdo* must be based on the analysis of numerous specimens from studied area. Single similar specimens could be found in very distant geographical regions, in all subspecies. That is why the demonstration of such specimens (Miroshnikov, 2022) cannot be a decisive argument for uniting of different populations into one subspecies.

The species is one of the biggest and most attractive representatives of European beetles. Earlier (Rudnev, 1953) it was regarded as the most dangerous pest of *Quercus*. Now it is included in the red data books of about all European countries including Russia, as well as in the red data books of several European Russian regions. A huge literature is devoted to various aspects of the biology of the species. A relatively vast revue was published by Miroshnikov (2019).

Results

Cerambyx (s. str.) *cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758

Figs 1-6

- Cerambyx cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758: 392 - "Habitat in Italia. M. Kähler. in Germania"; Lucas, 1847: 485 (= *paludivagus* Lucas, 1842), part. - "dans les bois marécageux du lac Tonga (environs du cercle de Lacalle)"; Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 (= *heros* Scopoli, 1763) - "Europa"; Aurivillius, 1912: 52 (= *heros* Scopoli) - "Mittel- und Südeuropa", including var. *acuminatus* Motsch. - "Krim", *manderstjernae* Muls. & God. - "Syrien", var. *mirbeckii* Lucas - "Mittelmeergebiet", var. *pfisteri* Stierl. - "Sicilien"; Plavilstshikov, 1940: 91, 635 (including ssp. *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864; ssp. *mirbeckii* Lucas, 1842; ssp. *acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853) - West Europe northwards to Sweden, most of Ukraine, Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Asia Minor, Syria, Iran, North Africa; Medvedev, Bozhko & Shapiro, 1951: 310 - Northern Donets near Svyatogorsk, Provallia Steppe, 314 - steppe zone and south forest-steppe; Arnoldi, 1953: 179, 185 - eastwards to about Volga, Tellerman, Zmiev, Svyatogorsk; Skufiy, 1978: 76 - southeast of the black-earth center (Voronezh Region with neighbor parts of Lipetsk and Belgorod regions; Villiers, 1978: 302 - "l'Europe centrale et méridionale, l'Afrique du Nord, le Caucase, l'Asie Mineure jusque dans l'Iran septentrional"; Khalidov, 1995: 140 - Tatarstan; Vives, 2000: 118; Magdeev, 2003: 207 - Samara Region, Zhiguli; Sama, 2003: 52 (= *heros* Scopoli, 1763); 2010: 50 (= *iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951); Isaev, 2004: 65 - Ulyanovsk Region; Isaev et al., 2004: 38 - Ulyanovsk Region; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004: 53 - Chernigov Region, Central Dnieper region, Donetsk Region; Tsurikov, 2006: 190 - Lipetsk Region; 2009: 211 - Lipetsk Region; Shumik, 2012: 30 - Krasnyi Styag, Pochep District, Bryansk Region; Polumordvinov & Monakhov, 2017: 286-287 - Penza Region, Neverkino district, Staraya Andreevka (Kadada River); 2019: 48 - Penza Region; Dyachenko, 2018: 49 - Kursk Region: whole European Russia; Glushkovo and L'gov districts; Miroshnikov, 2022: 254 - Europe, West Asia, North Africa.
- Cerambyx heros* Scopoli, 1763: 51 - "Circa Labacum".
- Hamaticherus mirbeckii* Lucas, 1842: 184 - "Assez commune dans le cercle de la Calle"; "dans les bois des lacs Houheira et Tonga"; Algérie.
- Cerambyx mirbeckii*, Lucas, 1847: 484, part. - "dans les bois des lacs Tonga et Houheira" (environs du cercle de Lacalle); "dans les bois de chênes-lièges qui se trouvent entre Stora et Philippeville"; Algérie.
- Cerambyx acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853: 79 - "Georgie et des pays limitrophes de la mer Caspienne".
- Cerambyx manderstjernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855b: 280 [= 1855a: 180] - "la Crimée".
- Hamaticherus pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864: 152 - "Sicilien", "vorzugsweise in der Gegend von Palermo, aber auch in andern Theilen der Insel".

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- Cerambyx cerdo* [locale Rasse] *acuminatus*, Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 (= *manderstjernae* Muls.) - “Krimm, Caucasus, Türkei, Kleinasien, Syrien”.
- Cerambyx cerdo* [locale Rasse] *pfisteri*, Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 - “Sicilien, Griechenland”.
- Cerambyx cerdo* [locale Rasse] *mirbeckii*, Ganglbauer, 1882: 744 - “Südfrankreich, Spanien, Corsica, Algier”.
- Hammaticherus cerdo*, Sakharov, 1903: 65 - Balashov district of Saratov Region.
- Cerambyx cerdo cerdo*, Plavilstshikov, 1940: 91, 635 (= *heros* Scopoli, 1763), part. - West Europe northwards to Sweden, west of Ukraine eastwards to about Kharkov; Villiers, 1978: 304 - “Europe centrale et méridionale”; Sama, 2003: 53, part. (= *acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 = *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864 = *mirbeckii* Lucas, 1842); 2011: 549 - Sardinia; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 159 (= *acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 = *heros* Scopoli, 1763 = *iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951 = *klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 = *manderstjernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855 = *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864), part. - Europe eastwards to Ukraine, Caucasus, Near East; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 134 - Italy; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2012: 201 - “Europa centrale e meridionale, in quella settentrionale fino alla Svezia; Africa sett., Cascao, Asia Minore, Iran”; Sama et al., 2012: 29 - Turkey; Sláma, 2019: 199, part.; Vartanis, 2023: 762, part. - “Czechia, Hungary, Austria, France, Italy, Croatia, Slovakia, Ukraina, Moldavia, Turkey, Polonia, Macedonia”.
- Cerambyx cerdo mirbecki*, Villiers, 1946: 78-79 - Maroc, Algérie, Tunisie.
- Cerambyx cerdo iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951: 156, 157 - “Soud-ouest de l'Iran, Bushir dans le Golfe perse”; Villiers, 1967b: 353, part. - “Iran: Bushir”; Sláma, 2019: 200, 201, part.; Danilevsky, 2020a: 71, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo morpha laevicollis* Heyrovský, 1955: 156 (unavailable name) - Třeboň environs (Czech Republic), after private letter (2023) by M. Sláma.
- Cerambyx cerdo acuminatus*, Villiers, 1967a: 20 - “Turquie”; 1967b: 353, part. - “Crimée, Asie Mineure, Arménie, Caucase, Nord de l'Iran”; Sláma, 2019: 203, part. - “eastern areas”; Miroshnikov, 2022: 259 (= *manderstjernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855); Vartanis, 2023: 762, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo mirbeckii*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Propio de Argelia, Túnez y Marruecos”; Vives, 2000: 118-119 - “la única presente en la región ibero-baleár”; “en Africa del Norte”, “en toda la Península [Ibérica] e islas Baleares”; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 159 (= *tunisicus* Pic, 1891), part. - Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia; Sláma, 2019: 204, part. - “North Africa”; Danilevsky, 2020a: 71, part.; Vartanis, 2023: 762, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo mirbeckii* var. *tunisicus*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Túnez”.
- Cerambyx cerdo cerdo* var. *acuminatus*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Dalmacia, Crimea, Cáucaso, Turmenia [sic], Turquía, Siria, Irán etc.”.
- Cerambyx cerdo cerdo* var. *pfisteri*, Compte-Sart & Carreras-Torrent, 2016: 88, part. - “Italia, Grecia y al parecer de Francia y Córcega”.

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- Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo acuminatus*, Cocquempot & al., 2016: 96, part. - Liban; Lazarev, 2019a: 22, 52, part. - “De la Georgie et des pays limitrophes de la mer Caspienne”; 2019b: 1257, part. - lectotype label: “Turkmenia Georgia”; Danilevsky, 2020c: 215, part. (= *klinzigi* Podaný, 1964) - south of European Russia, Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Near East; Miroschnikov, 2021: 459, 463 (= *manderstjerna* Mulsant & Godart, 1855), part.; Gubin & Martynov, 2023: 160 - Donetsk Region, Svyatogorsk environs.
- Cerambyx cerdo masaryki* Vartanis, 2018: 76 - “Bulgaria”; 2023: 760, 762, part. - “Bulgaria”.
- Cerambyx iranicus* [?], Sláma, 2019: 202, part.
- Cerambyx cerdo pfisteri*, Villiers, 1978: 304 - “Sicile et s’étend jusqu’en Grèce”; Sláma, 2019: 204, part. - “Corsica and Sicily”; Danilevsky, 2020a: 71, part.; Vartanis, 2023: 762, part. - “Greece, Italy”.
- Cerambyx cerdo manderstjerna*, Danilevsky, 2020b: 3 - Crimea and Black Sea coast (Sochi environs).
- Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo cerdo*, Danilevsky, 2020c: 215 - Europe.
- Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo manderstjerna*, Danilevsky, 2020c: 215 - south of European Russia, Ukraine.
- Cerambyx cerdo cyprius* Vartanis, 2023: 760 - “Cyprus”.

Description. Body dark brown, sometimes nearly black anteriorly, more or less lightened posteriorly; male antennae much longer than body; female antennae a little shorter or a little longer than body; 2nd antennal joint short, strongly transverse; 3rd and 4th antennal joints never strongly swollen; pronotum usually with numerous irregular plications sometimes more or less arranged transversely; very rare pronotum smooth and mirror-shiny as in *C. cerdo morpha laevicollis* Heyrovský, 1955 (population near Třeboň, Czech Republic); elytra strongly (males) or slightly (females) narrowed backwards, more or less roughly sculptured anteriorly and nearly smooth posteriorly; body length: 23–55 mm.

Distribution. About whole Europe from Iberian Peninsula to about Urals (excluding northern and desert regions without oaks), North Africa, Caucasus with Transcaucasia, Near East eastwards to Iran.

The problem of taxonomic interpretation of Eastern European populations of *C. cerdo* has long been recognized by entomologists (Polumordvinov & Monakhov, 2007). Below poorly known populations from Central Russia are recognized as a new subspecies.

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***Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo nikolaevi* ssp. n.**

Figs 1-2, Map 1

Hammaticherus cerdo, Sakharov, 1903: 65 - Balashov district of Saratov Region.

Cerambyx cerdo, Medvedev, Bozhko & Shapiro, 1951: 310 - Northern Donets near Svyatogorsk, Provallia Steppe, 314 - steppe zone and south forest-steppe; Arnoldi, 1953: 179, 185 - eastwards to about Volga, Tellerman, Zmiev, Svyatogorsk; Polozhentsev & Alekseev, 1959: 90 - Tellerman Forest; Skufyin, 1978: 76 - southeast of the black-earth center (Voronezh Region with neighbor parts of Lipetsk and Belgorod regions; Khalidov, 1995: 140 - Tatarstan; Magdeev, 2003: 207 - Samara Region, Zhiguli; Isaev, 2004: 65 - Ulyanovsk Region; Isaev et al., 2004: 38 - Ulyanovsk Region; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004: 53, part. - Chernigov Region, Central Dnieper region, Donetsk Region; Negrobov et al. 2005: 602 - Voronezh Region (Borisoglebsk District); Tsurikov, 2006: 190 - Lipetsk Region; 2009: 211 - Lipetsk Region; Shumik, 2012: 30 - Krasnyi Styag, Pochep District, Bryansk Region; Dyachenko, 2018: 49 - Kursk Region: Glushkovo and L'gov districts; Negrobov & Maslova, 2018: 273 - Voronezh Region (Borisoglebsk District); Prisyi, 2019: 432 - Belgorod Region (districts: Borisovka, Prokhorovka, Shebekino, Valuyki);

Cerambyx (s. str.) *cerdo acuminatus*, Gubin & Martynov, 2023: 160 - Donetsk Region, Svyatogorsk environs.

Type locality. Russia, Samara, Barboshina Polyana.

Description. Body big, similar to the biggest specimens of the other European and Caucasian populations; antennae moderately long, in males extending beyond elytral apex with 2 or 3 apical joints; female antennae significantly shorter than elytra; prothorax with extremely rough pronotal sculpture similar to prothorax of *C. c. acuminatus*; anterior prothorax constriction without three regular plications; elytra more or less converging posteriorly with distinct apical spines; body length in available males: 50-63 mm, body length in available female: 54 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new subspecies is close to *C. c. acuminatus* because of rough pronotal sculpture. But *C. c. acuminatus* usually has anterior pronotal constriction with three regular transverse plications absent in *C. c. nikolaevi*, as well as in *C. c. cerdo*. Antennae in *C. c. nikolaevi* distinctly shorter than in *C. c. cerdo* or in *C. c. acuminatus*.

Material. Holotype, male, Russia, Kuybyshev (now Samara), Frunze Polyana (now Barboshina Polyana), 24.5.1975. S. Kitanin leg. -

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author's collection; 3 paratypes; 1 male, Samara Region, Zhiguli, 1969, D. Natura leg. - author's collection; 1 male, Donetsk Region, Slavyansk District, Bogorodichnoe environs (near Svyatogorsk), 18.07.1972 - collection of Donetsk University, biological faculty; 1 female, Donetsk Region, Slavyansk District, Bogorodichnoe environs (near Svyatogorsk), 26.06.1971 - collection of Donetsk University, biological faculty.

Distribution. The subspecies is widely distributed all around central part of European Russia (according to Dyachenko, 2017 - whole European Russia) and Eastern Ukraine. Known localities are: Samara; Bakhteevka environs, Ulyanovsk Region; Staraya Andreevka environs, Penza Region; Orenburg Region (no exact locality); Tatarstan (no exact locality); Cheboksary; Tellerman Forest, Voronezh Region; Lipetsk Region (no exact locality); L'gov environs, Kursk Region; Glushkovo environs, Kursk Region; Krasnyi Styag, Bryansk Region; Prokhorovka environs, Belgorod Region.

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1-2 - *Cerambyx cerdo nikolaevi* **ssp. n.**: 1 - holotype, male, Russia, Kuybyshev (now Samara), Frunze Polyana (now Barboshina Polyana), 24.5.1975. S. Kitanin leg. (author's photo); 2 - paratype, female, Donetsk Region, Bogorodichnoe environs near Svyatogorsk, 26.06.1971 - photo by A. Gubin.

3-4 - *Cerambyx cerdo cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758 (author's photos): 3 - male, Ukraine, Kirovograd Region, Znamenka, 16-23.6.2017, L. Demidova leg.; 4 - female with same label.

5-6 *Cerambyx cerdo acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 (author's photos): 5 - male, Armenia, Megri, 30.6.2003 M. Danilevsky leg.; 6 - female, Azerbaijan, Avrora (now Hirkan), 11.06.1979, M. Danilevsky leg.

Map 1. Locations of *Cerambyx* (s. str.) *cerdo nikolaevi* ssp. n.

1 - Samara; 2 - Bakhteevka environs, Ulyanovsk Region; 3 - Staraya Andreevka environs, Penza Region; 4 - Orenburg Region (no exact locality); 5 - Tatarstan (no exact locality); 6 - Cheboksary; 7 - Tellerman Forest, Voronezh Region; 8 - Lipetsk Region (no exact locality); 9 - L'gov environs, Kursk Region; 10 - Glushkovo environs, Kursk Region; 11 - Krasnyi Styag, Bryansk Region; 12 - Prokhorovka environs, Belgorod Region; 13 - Borisovka environs, Belgorod Region; 14 - Shebekino environs, Belgorod Region; 15 - Valuyki environs, Belgorod Region; 16 - Svyatogorsk environs, Donetsk Region.

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